

NDAC/LO/120
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Results of the first full-scale simulation of the Sphere Solution etc
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(as reported at NDAC meeting in Lund, 1988 July 6)

Introduction

In June 1988, the first full-scale simulation of Step 2/3 (sphere solution and astrometric parameter determination) was successfully carried out at Lund Observatory. The simulation comprised 114,488 stars (IC1) observed in 2048 sets (2.5 years), or a total of 3,999,975 abscissae. The 'observations' (abscissae) were simulated with realistic random and systematic errors, the latter including a sun-related harmonic modulation of the basic angle (of the order of 0.1 milli-arcsec) and correlations within each set as expected from the geometric great-circle reductions. However, no slit errors were included in this simulation.

Abscissa data were generated in the format that was then foreseen for sending the real data from Copenhagen to Lund (GCOS-1, C Petersen, March '87) and put on two magnetic tapes.

The star catalogue, however, was not 'imported' according to the interface specification (GCOS-1), but was taken over as a disc file (with reasonable a priori errors) from the simulations. The reason for this is that the first program module, PREP23, is not yet available.

Program execution

The table below shows the sequence in which the program modules were run and the approximate execution times (real times, not CPU times) on the observatory's HP9000 Series 530 computer:

SORT23	17 hours				
LOAD23	2 hours				
ACCU23	66 hours	(first pass, full matrix)			
SOLV23	16 hours	" " " "			
ACCU23	12 hours	(second pass, rhs only)			
SOLV23	< 1 hours	" " " "			
ACCU23	36 hours	(third pass, rhs only)			
SOLV23	81 hours	(third pass, rhs + zero point variances)			

TOTAL:	230 hours				

No provision was made to 'fix' the normals, i.e. to remove the expected rank deficiency. No singular columns were detected. The

condition number of the normals was estimated at 4,000,000 and the maximum number of bits lost in the Cholesky reduction was 6 (to be compared with the double-precision mantissa length of 55 bits).

Results for the global parameters

The solution included seven global parameters, namely the harmonic coefficients of order 1, 2, 3, and 6 of the abscissa difference w.r.t. the sun (the coefficient for $\sin v$ was not included, since it is almost indistinguishable from a global shift of the parallax zero point). The table below gives the true and estimated parameters with standard errors from the solution:

Term	Coefficient [micro-arcsec]		(est - true)/s.e.
	true	estimated	
cos v	0	2 +- 4	+0.6
sin 2v	0	2 +- 3	+0.5
cos 2v	0	1 +- 3	+0.2
sin 3v	100	102 +- 3	+0.7
cos 3v	0	-1 +- 3	-0.4
sin 6v	0	2 +- 3	+0.5
cos 6v	40	38 +- 3	-0.8

Global orientation of the resulting system

The adjusted astrometric parameters (excluding the parallaxes) were compared with the true values and the differences were analysed in terms of a global misorientation/rotation of the reference frame. The abscissa zero point corrections were similarly analysed. Using different combinations of these data resulted in slightly different estimates of the orientation and rotation parameters, as shown in the table below.

Differences used	Orient [micro-arcsec]			Rot [micro-arcsec/year]		
	x	y	z	x	y	z
RA & pm_RA	7	16	111	20	151	-334
Dec & pm_Dec	-30	16	-	12	178	-
pos & pm	-20	16	109	15	171	-337
zero points	-34	15	116	20	163	-330
adopted values:	-27	15	113	15	168	-333

The general agreement is rather good, however. It is especially satisfying that the analysis based on the astrometric differences (pos & pm) agrees very well with the analysis based on the zero point differences; the two analyses differ by 22 micro-arcsec in orientation and by 12 micro-arcsec/year in rotation.

Error statistics for the astrometric parameters

After correction for the adopted system orientation and rotation errors, the mean and rms errors ($d = \text{estimated} - \text{true}$) of the astrometric parameters were as follows:

Parameter	< d >	d_RMS	Skewness
RA*cos(Dec)	-0.004 mas	1.07 mas	
Dec	-0.017 mas	0.89 mas	
parallax	+0.012 mas	1.30 mas	-0.002 +- 0.011
pm_RA*cos(Dec)	-0.006 mas/year	1.53 mas/year	
pm_Dec	-0.000 mas/year	1.23 mas/year	

The figures below show the distributions of individual errors d for each of the astrometric parameters. The last figure shows the standard errors of the 2048 abscissa zero points plotted against the set number.

